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The Contribution of Internal Assurance System to Increase Learning Quality

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Abstract

The National Standards of Education (NSE) plays an important role in controlling the quality of education because it contains some aspects for the educational system. The purpose of this research is to strengthen the implementation of the education quality assurance system. This study used a combination of a quantitative and qualitative approach. Data was 33.664 for quality report assessment at elementary schools in academic year 2016/2017 combined with the result of questionnaire and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with teachers, the school principal, and school supervisors in Yogyakarta City and Tarakan City. The results of statistical analysis indicate only process standard, graduate competency standard, financing standard, and assessment standard that have already achieved the level of NSE 4. The lowest value achieved is the educator standards (3.18), which means that the qualifications of educators are still relatively low. Research also found out that the Internal Quality Assurance System (IQAS) gives a benefit to improve the learning quality while FGD shows that almost all standards affect the graduate competency standard.

Keywords: Education, Quality Assurance, Quality Report, Learning, Elementary School

Introduction

Every citizen has the same rights to obtain a quality education as it is stated in article 5 of Law No 20 Year 2003, where the government has an obligation in the implementation of quality education. Therefore, in realizing the quality education, the government issued a government regulation No. 19 year 2005 on National Standards of Education (NSE) that has undergone a change twice in year 2013. By applying curriculum 2013, then the government issued a government regulation of Republic of Indonesia number 32 year 2013 about changes to government Regulation number 19 year 2005 about NSE and in 2015 the government revises became Government regulation of the Republic of Indonesia number 13 year 2015 about NSE. The changes in the article provide improvements to the expected quality education. In line with this, the government also issued MOEC regulation No 28 of 2016 on the basic and secondary education quality assurance system. The quality improvement system aims to ensure the fulfillment of standards in the system of education, which is systemic, holistic, and sustainable. Therefore, quality cultures grow and develop in the unit of education independently.

Education quality assurance system as in the regulation consists of five cycles, namely 1) quality mapping, 2) preparation of the fulfillment plan, 3) implementation of the fulfillment plan, 4) evaluation/audit, implementation of the plan, and 5) determination the quality standards. (Director General of Primary and Secondary Education, MOEC, 2016). By implementing those entire cycles of internal quality assurance system independently and continuously, it is expected to develop a quality culture in the education unit.

In general, education quality assurance frameworks in schools have the following traits: 1) quality assurance is based on general, open and objective performance indicators formulated based on the statements, which serve as a quality assessment tool for education in schools. 2) quality assurance is done through a transparent and interactive process through self-assessment and quality assurance section. 3) quality assurance is conducted with respect to the strengths of various activities in the quality assurance process and management, as well as the traditional values and needs of the school to change. 4) quality assurance is carried out by maintaining a balance between support to the school through partnerships and pressures to schools through monitoring. 5) quality assurance's purpose is to achieve the quality of school education through development and accountability (Meirawan, 2010).

While it is undoubtedly stated that Quality Assurance (QA) is merely a supporting mechanism, or a series of mechanisms, designed to promote high success (Tovey, 1994:97). The achievement of education quality in education unit is one indicator of the achievement of eight national education standards (content standards, process standards, valuation standards, educators and education personnel standards, management standards, facilities and infrastructure standards, and financing standards). Therefore, the education quality assurance system is required in the education unit to control the achievement of national education standards (Ministerial regulation No 28 Year 2016 where each unit of education have to form Internal Quality Assurance System (IQAS).

In the implementation of IQAS in the unit of education, the success factor is certainly not separated from the role of 1) effective headmaster leadership, 2) the involvement of teachers and educational personnel, 3) commitment and consistency of school citizens. In achieving the quality of the school, the role of the headmaster is very dominant to determine the resulting achievement. This is because the headmaster as a manager has the responsibility for the execution of all components under his leadership. The school principal performs the functions of education management together with the school citizen, and the School Committee (Kemal and Hasibuan, 2017). However, most of the school principal have little capacity to develop their school management, particularly conducting academic supervision due to their lack of competence for leadership. Therefore, in developing school management, he/she is supported by the supervisors who have experience in managing school (ACDP, 2013).

Implementation of quality assurance system has become a common thing in education (Doherty, 2008:255, DuMond and Thomas, 2013:128) where at the managerial and the organization level aims to achieve the performance that has been passed. Of course, this performance achievement is efforts to compete with the educational institutions through monitoring and evaluation towards an effective and efficient organization.

Implementation of quality management depends on the synergy of the leaders of educational institutions, quality assurance teams, stakeholders, work units in the application of quality, communication and customer satisfaction (Murniati, et al. 2018:9). Olaru and Paunescu (2004) state that implementing this system follows the stage 1) identifying all processes that have an impact on the quality of "Product", such as teaching, learning, and research, 2) determining the interaction between the unit of the process actors and develop communication systems, 3) determining the amount of resources needed to create an effective and efficient organizational atmosphere, and 4) determining the objectives that are related to quality and set when the objectives will be achieved.

There are some definitions of quality. Quality is used to signify 'excellence' of a product or service and is used to demonstrate the superiority of a fruitful product or service (Oakland, 1993:5) which means conformance to requirements (Macdonald, 1993:6) and the quality of the fit is a measure of how far a product meets the

requirements or quality specifications that have been set to demonstrate its ability to meet the needs, expectations, and customer satisfaction. (Tjiptono and Diana, 1995:2), perceived service quality is an important concept on the quality management field (Sumaedi and Bakti, 2011:81).

Numerous researchers have investigated the relationship between perceived service quality and customer's satisfaction to perceive service quality, which affects customer satisfaction. Many researchers have examined the relationship between perceived service quality and customer satisfaction and come up with service quality to perceive as influencing customer satisfaction. Quality in education includes the calculation of graduation and total student levels, the absorption rate of alumni in employment and wage rates, the level of placement of students in further education, test scores and standards, efficient use of resources, timely reporting and accountability, education accessibility for everyone, class size and teacher-to-student ratio, evaluation based on teaching, developing students' ability to apply new learning practices, encouragement and facilitation in lifelong learning, opportunity professional development for lecturers, the use of learning for students, the development of active skills and habits as citizens, the development of critical awareness, the creation of togetherness, an environment of mutual respect and mutual learning among students and teachers, and guaranteed freedom for discussion for students and teacher (Worthen Berry, 2002) and education challenges include changes in the educational environment, global competition, customer demands, economic demands, and social development (Kalolo, 2015).

The emergence of data on the quality of education in Indonesia is existing because of some reasons. The learning process that is not in line with expectations is one of the factors that contribute to the low quality of education. A reality faced by the world of education in formal education institutions today is the low managerial quality of learning both at the level of planning, implementation, and how to control it. Therefore, reconstruction of the management of learning programs is absolutely necessary to achieve the expected goals (Manopo, 2014: 187). Basically, the Internal Quality Assurance System (IQAS) refers to the standard setting cycle, standard implementation, standard evaluation, standard control, and standard improvement (Wasis and Andi, 2016: 1). However, for reasons of efficient QAS maintenance, QAS designers may prefer a standard system for all schools (Vischer, 2009).

Salgado et al. (2014: 357) argue that "Quality Management System (QMS) is designed to improve the performance of organizational goals to improve their seeking to overcome their results constantly. From the above opinion, it can be interpreted that the Quality Management System (QMS) is designed to continuously improve the performance of organizations that aim to improve their services, trying to overcome their results continuously. These change efforts are characterized by wave after wave of programs – education and training initiatives for all employees, continuous changes in structure, the development of mission and value statements, or initiatives such as re-engineering and total quality management (Locke (2009:541-542).

Okwiri & Mbeche (2014: 209) state that "ISO 9001: 2008 is as pro-mote process approach, a fundamental principle of quality management, and therefore, the expectation from certification would be to focus on products and processes of producing the products and services ". From the above opinion, it can be interpreted that ISO 9001: 2008 strives to promote process approach, the basic principles of quality management. Therefore, the expectations of certification will refocus far away from the product and for the process of producing products and services.

One characteristic of the 21st century is the increasingly direct and indirect interaction of the citizens of the world supported by the advancement of Information and Communication Technology. Then, the reflective question is: Have we selected and prepared our students to take on the role? Have we got students to think critically in response to various information, so the hoaxes are not affected or become successors to hoax information? The reluctance of thinking Chris raises an anecdote that the speed of movement of the thumb in the present exceeds the speed of the brain to think. It is easy for someone to pass on information (thanks to technology) without checking the truth of the information. The P21 organization (www.p21.org) in the United States is one of the developers of the 21st-century educational framework, and many have made it a reference. Three skills that must be possessed in the 21st century according to p21 are (1) life and career skills, (2) learning

and innovation skills, and (3) information media and technology skills. More specifically for learning and innovation skills, there are 4 competencies that must be possessed (known as 4C), namely: Communication, Collaboration, Critical Thinking, and Creativity. British Council introduces Core Skills (skills), namely skills that must be possessed in the 21st century, including skills: critical thinking and problem solving, creativity and imagination, leadership, digital literacy, collaboration and communication, and citizenship.

The World Economic Forum organization publishes that there have been major changes to the demands of skills in 2020 compared with 2015. The top rankings are (1) Complex Problem Solving; (2) Critical Thinking (ranked 4th in 2015), and (3) Creativity (ranked 10th in 2015). The source gives us an idea of what the community needs in the 21st century. Higher education and education instincts must respond to these needs through the adaptive curriculum and learning processes. The learning process is at the core of all school activities, manifested in the form of student-teacher interactions aimed at students having academic, economic, social, personal, and religious abilities. In the learning process, the main activity of students is learning, and the main activity of the teacher is teaching, so the dimensions of learning and teaching are the main focus in the School Quality Assurance (SQA). Based on the description above, the Office of Educational Research and Education Centre, MOEC reviews the actual issue of the education quality assurance system on its implementation in educational units. The purpose of this study is to develop policy recommendations for strengthening the education quality assurance system. The detailed purpose of this research is to analyze: 1) achievement of report cards/education quality maps on the readiness to meet the National Education Standards. 2) relationship of achievement of Graduates' Competency Standards with achievement of the learning process (standard content, process, assessment of learning), and supporting the learning process (Educator and education personnel, Facilities and infrastructure, Management, and Financing Standards), 3) obstacle and supporting factors in the implementation of quality assurance education. The scope/limitation of the study of the education quality assurance system is eight national standards of education at the elementary level. This is because the elementary school is in the level in which the data entered is bigger and complete, so this study concentrates on the elementary school level.

Method

This research used a quantitative and qualitative approach. Data used was secondary data from the results of the Directorate of Basic and Secondary Education (DBSE) about education quality assurance system. The primary data was collected through questionnaires and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with school principals, teachers, school supervisors, and regional education offices in Yogyakarta City and Tarakan City. The analysis of the safety of eight national education standards was used to determine the extent of the quality report card which can contribute to the fulfillment of national education standards and to find out how the learning process by the teacher towards the achievement of the learning process as well as the supporting and inhibiting factors for the implementation of the education quality assurance system.

Results and Discussion

1. Achievement of National Standard Education Report/Quality Map for Accreditation Readiness.

a. Achievement of Quality Report Card on each standard

Analysis of the achievements of each national education standard needs to be done to prepare for the achievement of accreditation as an indicator of education quality. The achievements of each of standards were analyzed based on 2017 data from National Standards Agency of Standards Secondary School (NSASS), Ministry of Education and Culture MOEC). Data of the results of the quality report achievement 33,664 elementary schools was obtained from the results of the educational quality assurance system. The achievement of report cards for each NSE will be mapped based on the indicator values, as stated in the categories I – V.

b. Achievement of the QAS in the elementary school

From all the standards, the performance of education, which is related to the quality of education, especially the level of basic education, still does not show good quality yet. Based on data from QAS achievements per standard, a list of QAS achievements towards NSE is prepared at the elementary school level data for 2016-2017, as shown in Table 4.9 below.

Table 1, Achievement of QAS shows NSE at the level of elementary school data for 2016-2017.

Category	Indicator	Average value	Standard	Value	Category	M1	M2	M3	M4	NSE	Total
I	To NSE 1	0 – 2,04	Content	5.54	****	51		6,491	26,361	-	33,664
II	To NSE 2	2,05 – 3,70	Process	6.40	****	51	457		17,449	14,773	33,664
III	To NSE 3	3,71 – 5,06	Graduate competency	5.96	****	101	560	866	27,203	4,934	33,664
IV	To NSE 4	5,07 – 6,66	Educators	3.18	**	1,236	26,470	5,958	-	-	33,664
V	Meets NSE	6,67 – 7,00	Facilities and infrastructure	4.14	***	1,399	2,918	29,347	-	-	33,664
			Management	5.62	****		1,270	4,781	27,411	-	33,664
			Financing	5.70	****	32	1,085	3,525	28,515	507	33,664
			Assessment	5.81	****	247	729	4,855	23,926	3,907	33,664

The data indicates that the standard has not fulfilled the NSE is content standard, educator and education personnel standard, facilities, and infrastructure standard and management standard. Some primary schools have already fulfilled the process standard, graduate competency standard, valuation standard, and financing standard. Nevertheless, most have not fulfilled the standard when viewed from the assessment of the quality report.

It is suspected that the assessment of quality reports is used to see the overall achievement of any standard from some respondents as diagnostic data. QAS instruments with viewing coverage 1) standard, 2) indicators, 3) Sub indicators, and 4) question items. QAS respondents are addressed to school supervisors, school principals, teachers, students, and parents' representatives. Standard measurements are conducted by NSASS for the achievement accreditation of each standard. Accreditation devices are organized by grid loading; 1) standard, 2) components, 3) aspects, 4) indicators, 5) question points, and 6) tennis instructions. Principal respondents, teachers, and more on the standard document-proof.

Therefore, the assessment result of the quality report can predict the lack of achievement on each standard, then the instrument or device needs to be done synchronization so the quality report data can be used as the basic accreditation of education units.

2. Graduate Competency Standard Achievement Relationship with learning process achievement (content, process, learning assessment), and supporting learning process (PTK, facilities and infrastructure, management, and financing)

In 2017, a team of Directorate of Basic and Secondary Education, MOEC has been collecting data about 52,976 school models and nonschool models. The data characteristics obtained from eight national standards of which each of the standard consists of indicators and sub-indicators, and this data is processed in aggregate of each national education standard.

Relationships between 8 NSE is also analyzed by using the assumption that the achievement of competency standards graduates are directly affected only by the access of the standard process, while the access to the process standards directly influenced by the achievement of six other standards. This model with 2 relationships between 8 standards is illustrated in the following image.

Figure IV-2: Model 2 relationships between eight national education standards Standardize Solution (Factor Loading) (N = 52,976)

1. From six standards (educators, content, financing, management, appraisal, and facilities and infrastructure), only the facilities and infrastructure standard which does not have a significant effect on the process. The other five standards are statistically significant.
2. The model shows only the achievement of the standard process that has a significant and most are a meaningful influence on the achievement of the Graduation Standards (GS).

The model demonstrates that the standards of educators, content, financing, management, appraisal and facilities and infrastructure, have a small influence on the standard of the process. While the standard of the process has a significant influence on the graduate competency standards. This happens because the most major standard in influencing the graduate competency standard at the primary level is the process standard played by the teacher. This is in accordance with the development of the child that the child which are at the elementary school level still needs a lot of guidance directly portrayed by the teacher. Teachers in implementing the learning process become central figures to provide guidance to elementary school. The success of education at primary school level can be suspected influenced more if it is done by professional teachers. Teacher's participation in program induction, ICT training, and seminar /workshops that are significantly related to the quality of universal elementary education in the state of Lagos (Akpan and Ita, 2015). It is recommended that governments and related institutions need to intensify the provision efforts for the professional development of teachers through in-service education to improve the quality of the elementary school. Governments and related institutions should provide more opportunities for teachers to attend ICT training programs to enhance their instructional teaching activities.

Although six standards (educators, content, financing, management, assessment and facilities, and infrastructure) have a limited contribution to the progress of the learning process, however, those standards may still have the advantage to improve learning process when equipped with adequate means.

This idea is tested with a relationship model illustrated in the following figure, where the moderator variable, which is a multiplication between the educator variables and the supporting variables, is assumed to give additional influence on the achievement of the process standard.

Figure IV-3: Model 3 relationship eight national standards of education with variable moderators. standardize solution (loading factor)

Richardson, Bhuiya, Islam. Misuddin et al. (2018) explain that:

"All over the world, education systems are facing a big challenge to ensure all children have access to quality educators. In the context of Rangpur District, Bangladesh, it is very inspiring and notable that teachers have improved their pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, and assessment skills significantly, through their participation in the quality educators for every child project in Bangladesh. Nevertheless, findings indicate further areas for improvement to ensure quality educators not only for Bangladesh but also for similar regions of the world.

Throughout the world, the education system faces major challenges to ensure all children to have to access the qualified educators. In the context of Rangpur District, Bangladesh, it is very inspiring and noteworthy that teachers have increased significantly in pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, and their assessment skills, through their participation in the project quality educators for every child in Bangladesh. Nevertheless, the findings show further areas for improvement to ensure the quality of educators not only for Bangladesh but also for similar territories in the world.

From the statistical test results to this model obtain the following information.

T-VALUES (significant)

- a. The moderator variables (educator vs. supporters) have a positive and significant impact on achieving process standards. The influence of the achievement of the standards of educators on the learning process (content, process, assessment) proved to be strengthened by the achievement of supporting standards (facilities and infrastructure, management, financing).
- b. The subsequent achievement of the standard process has a significant and positive influence on the achievement of graduation standards. The higher the achievement of the standard process, the higher the achievement of the graduate competency standard.

Based on this model test, the moderator variables which are the multiplication of the educator variables and the supporting variables (facilities and infrastructure, management, financing) jointly significantly affect the learning process (content, process, judgment). Similarly, the learning process variables significantly affect the competency standards of graduates. That is, the competency standards of the graduates in the elementary school level are strongly influenced by the implementation of the learning process and teacher role in the implementation of learning activities.

The results show that (1) the ability of Indonesian elementary school teachers in preparing instructional media still need to be maximized. Although the quantity of its existence has been in accordance with the provisions of the National Education Standards Agency, however, the quality can only reach an average of 9.78%; (2) the problems faced by elementary school teachers in preparing learning media, namely: (a) unclear technical guidelines for the preparation of the curriculum and syllabus; (b) lesson plan is developed limitedly in administrative needs; (c) learning materials did not analyze optimally; (d) instructional media did not designed properly; (e) the determination of evaluation tool and follow-up of learning was still very limited; (3) in designing learning devices, teachers need to understand some aspects, such as (a) the design of lesson plans, (b) the development of learning models and methods, (c) the development of media and teaching aids, (d) The development of learning implementation scenarios, and (e) the development of learning evaluation devices (La Ode, Turi, Ahiri, La Dunifa, Ardiansyah, 2017).

3. Implementation of an education quality assurance system

a. Teacher Analysis

Changes occurring in the learning process after the Internal Quality Assurance System (IQAS)

Tarakan City

The discussion in this city came up with the conclusion that there is a change in the implementation of the learning process after IQAS. The change is in the form of the students who begin to understand the learning material. This easiness is gotten because the students are used to obtain the information through the internet. The teacher's perception shows that the school is better, better prepared, and more steady in handling problems in schools, so students' learning outcomes improved although it still needs some improvement. The IQAS's motivates the teachers and students are able to interact better. Therefore, the school IQAS shows a change, especially in the implementation of the learning process performed by the teacher. This will affect the achievement of more effective learning outcomes.

Cities in Yogyakarta

There is a significant change in the elementary school of Timuran in the student-oriented learning process as the subject of the students' character enhancement learning. In addition, at elementary school of Bayangkara with IQAS learning process becomes more directional in accordance with Learning Plan designed with the team of class teachers Subject Teacher Working Group (STWG) following school principal's instruction. Besides, it also happens at elementary school of Tegalmulyo which is a change in the learners, and they are increasingly passionate with activities to add to the children's quality in the field of morality and educational habits. This is influenced by the school program after IQAS. Then an elementary school of Muhammadiyah

Nitikan makes changes by making the learning process more conditioned and better organized, learning media are also better prepared so the teachers are ready in the process of teaching learning and will affect on achieving a more maximal outcome in students compared before. One very beneficial way of giving a fresh perspective on teaching is to undertake a 'teacher placement,' and it is vital that performance management is seen as an opportunity to analyze their progress, to identify training needs and to have them met (Donnelly, 2002:80-81).

b. Principal

The role of the school principal in filling instruments of Education Quality Assurance System (QAS). Direct involvement of the principal in the filling of QAS instruments is not the same between schools. Most of the fulfillment is done by the assigned team. The team consists of teachers and employees of the administration staff, which primarily handle the fulfilment of the eight NSE. The benefits of mapping the quality of Education Quality Assurance System (QAS) on the improvement of Compliance eight standards, according to the principal.

- **Content Standard**
Measurement results can be used as a guide for teachers to improve the material that will be presented to students. From the results of measurements, the description of what has been and is not fulfilled can be used as an evaluation material to make repairs through the arrangement in the next year. It also makes it easier to know which items should be prioritized, which can later be included in the preparation of the School Budget Activities Plan (SBAP).
- **Process Standard**
The measuring results of process standard improve teacher's understanding in carrying out the learning process, which also influences the improvement of the preparation of learning media. Therefore, it can be used as an evaluation material for the teaching-learning process. Then, it can be used as a reference for improvement by the teacher because the QAS instrument is closely related to the input and outcome in the process standard.
- **Graduate Competence Standard**
The QAS measurement results are used as a guide for schools in determining graduation standards. The results of these measurements also encourage teachers to have a better understanding about students' needs and pay attention to things that are able to develop students' potential. Besides, this measurement can also be used as material to analyze shortcomings to develop a strategy to achieve standard graduation.
- **Educators and Teacher Standards**
The performance and qualifications of educators and teacher can be seen from the results of QAS measurements. Therefore, they can be used as a reference to improve the quality of human resources through the fulfillment and improvement of their performance and qualifications.
- **Facilities and Infrastructure Standard**
From the measurement results of QAS show facilities and infrastructure standard that must be equipped to meet the minimum service standard. It can determine the priority of facilities and infrastructure that must be completed through its procurement plan, as outlined in the School budget Activities Plan.
- **Management Standard**
The results data from QAS measurement can be used as a reference in school development planning in order to make improvements in meeting management standards. With this measurement, the principal understands the flow of school management to be more effective. Therefore, school managerial management can be better.
- **Financing Standard**
QAS data can be used as a reference in budget planning through the preparation of School Budget Activities Plan (SBAP) and can be used as a reference in improving the fulfillment of financial standards. The results of the QAS measurement can also be used as a reference in determining the priority scale of financing needs for improving students' achievement.
- **Assessment Standard**
It can be used as a guide in developing strategies and assessment standards for students. With the

measurement of QAS, the teacher also understands the assessment steps and tries to implement them according to the standards set.

c. School Supervisor

Quality mapping is done by spreading quality assurance instruments that contain hundreds of questions. The instruments are addressed to school principals, teachers, students, supervisors, and school committees. School's answers in QAS instruments are validated by the supervisor, then send to the center online. The role of supervisors as coaches, supervisors, and validators is very important in the education quality assurance process in schools. A large contribution that the Total Quality Movement made to the organization is the concept of continuous improvement, applied to train new supervisors (Jones and Chen, 2006:36).

Validation of Instruments Educational Quality Assurance System (QAS) is carried out by supervisors before the operator sent it online to the center. In Yogyakarta, a supervisor validated as many schools as they are trained. One supervisor, more or less fosters 21-25 schools. In contrast, in Tarakan, one supervisor conducted validation in a target school of one school for nine supervisors. The method for validating the contents of the Education Quality Assurance System instrument conducted by the supervisor.

The stages carried out by the supervisor in validating the instrument contents are: 1) Checking the instrument that has been filled in by the respondent; 2) Ensuring all respondents fill in the instrument; 3) Accounting the respondents whether it is in accordance with the provisions; 4) Having each instrument been filled in all; 5) What date did the data entry take place.

d. Obstacle in QAS

An obstacle faced by Public Elementary School 2 Tarakan in the implementation of the Internal Quality Assurance System in elementary schools includes inadequate conditions and the affordability of internet access available at school, and in the classroom condition that is too hot. Furthermore, the obstacle in Elementary School of 49 Tarakan are some educators who did not have the awareness to advance schools and lack of facilities and infrastructure in schools, for example, lack of classrooms, no halls, no space for studying Islam and Catholicism. The obstacle in the implementation of IQAS in Public Elementary School 12 Tarakan is the lack of awareness from the school in order to fulfill the standards of facilities and infrastructure and their follow-up. The obstacle in Public Elementary School 24 Tarakan is the lack of willingness of the school to try to improve and meet the standards of facilities and infrastructure.

It also happens in DIY, the obstacle in IQAS in Timuran Elementary Schools included facilities and infrastructure of schools. Besides, in Bhayangkara Elementary School, the instruments are too complicated, sometimes it is not in accordance with statements in the field. The next obstacle in the implementation of IQAS in Tegalmulyo Elementary School is the lack of complete and inadequate facilities for teaching and learning activities. The last obstacle comes from IQAS in Muhammadiyah Nitikan Elementary School, where the existence of activities outside of teaching and learning, so the administration of the administration is often late.

The principal expects some guidance to the school to implement IQAS properly. Coaching can be held by the Education Quality Assurance Board (EQAB) and supervisors through workshops followed by ongoing assistance. In order to support the implementation of IQAS in schools, almost all principals who participated in the FGD say need to support adequate facilities and infrastructure in their schools, such as computer equipment, printers, and internet networks. The constraints in conducting validation are 1) many assisted schools to have an impact on the number of instruments that must be validated, 2) number of instruments/questions in each respondent, and 3) instruments for students are difficult to understand. Next, the constraints in QAS instruments are 1) teachers and principals do not understand each cycle in Quality Assurance System (QAS) well because IQAS schools have not been implemented for a long time, 2) the respondent (students and the school committee) do not understand the terminology of instrument items, 3) there are some inappropriate statements, 4) their item of questionnaire for school principals and staff are relatively similar that make the data input confusing.

To improve the implementation of IQAS in schools, it is necessary to develop and strengthen the competencies of human resources in schools. The school needs assistance from to be Quality Assurance Agencies (QAA) to monitor the IQAS. In addition, the Subject Teacher Working Group (STWG) should give intensive and special training to teachers to strengthen school team.

All in all, the position is that whatever the variation between one company and another, as well as between one professional institution and another-systems of (or approaches to) QA must be grounded in an understanding of overall intent (Tovey, 1994: 168).

Conclusions and Recommendation

Conclusion

Based on the data and information obtained, it can be concluded as follows.

1. Based on data obtained from 33,664 elementary schools in 2016 and 2017 for the quality report card assessment shows that all criteria still do not meet the NSE category with an average value of 6.67 - 7.00. From the national standard set, only process standard, graduate competency standard, financing standard, and assessment standard that are already at the level towards NSE 4. Other standards are still at the low level towards NSE 4. The lowest value achieved is educators and education personnel standard (3.18). The low number is more for education personnel who have not met in accordance with standard provisions. While the highest value is achieved by the process standard (6.40). This figure shows that in general, the learning process in the elementary school education unit has run well.
2. From the analysis, results indicate that Graduation Standards (GS) is a very important standard in realizing education quality nationally. To support the achievement of GS, it takes roles and contributions to the achievement of the learning process (content, process, assessment of learning), and supporting the learning process (CAR, Facilities and infrastructure, Management, and Financing). The results of the analysis statistically show that almost all standards affect GS. The higher the achievement of process standards, the higher the achievement of the graduate competency standard. In this result, only the achievement of process standards has a significant and most significant influence on achieving the GS standard, while the standard achievement of the smallest effect on GS is the standard achievement of Facilities and infrastructure. Based on the achievement of quality report cards at the Primary School level, from 7 standards (Content, Process, Educators and education personnel, Facility and infrastructure, Management, Financing, and Learning Assessment) are able to predict the achievement of Graduates Competency Standards by 70.7%. The remaining 29.3% is explained by other factors, except for the achievements of seven standards.
3. Based on the results of the FGD with teachers, principals, and school supervisors is concluded that the benefits of IQAS can be felt in efforts to improve the quality of learning. At the level of implementation, after the existence of IQAS shows a change, especially in the implementation of the learning process carried out by the teacher. Changes in the learning process affect the achievement of more effective learning outcomes.

Having implemented IQAS, the benefits received include togetherness sense in having the school to advance the school and an increase in the discipline of teachers and students at school. There is a change in the quality/output that is better both academically and non-academically; the collaboration between teachers and parents is established in a better manner.

However, there are still obstacles in implementing IQAS, including limited facilities and infrastructure in schools (internet access, study rooms) and also a low sense of school's ownership by teachers and education staff. Another obstacle is the school does not enter the model school category. Therefore, it is not given the socialization and time to receive the instruments and the limited of re-submission of the instruments and make the filling of the QAS instruments is inaccurate.

Recommendation

1. Based on the results of the quality report cards produced, it shows that the achievement of the National Education Standards is almost all criteria do not meet the standard. The strategic steps are needed towards the achievement of standards that still have low scores. Therefore, both the central and the provincial as well as district government prioritize assistance to achieve the low standard at the level of elementary school education.
2. Graduates competency standard is influenced by the achievement of 7 standards (Content, process, educator and education personnel, facilities and infrastructure, management, financing, and learning assessment). Therefore, in the implementation of education units, especially in elementary schools, the role of seven national education standards needs to be prioritized, especially the achievement of standards of educators and education personnel.
3. The result of the analysis shows that the educator standard contributes to the success of the learning process significantly. It means that educators or teachers have a significant effect on students' learning success. Therefore, increasing teacher competency through training is needed to achieve the success of teachers' teaching.
4. The instrument of school principals and the supervisors is too long that make them boring to fill a questionnaire that makes the school principal and supervisors fill it inaccurately. Therefore, it is recommended that the instrument should be simple.

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Author contributions

Sabar B.R, Meni, H. Lia, Y, HM Noor, Idris design research, performed research, and data analyzed. Sabar B.R gives more contribution to the paper than other authors. All authors wrote the paper, proofread it, and approved the final manuscript.

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